

JAFAR JABBARLI AS A PROPHET OF WOMEN'S FREEDOM AND DEFENDER OF WOMEN'S RIGHTS

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Abstract

Jafar Jabbarli (1899–1934), one of the prominent representatives of 20th century Azerbaijani literature, is an artist who left a rich legacy in the fields of dramaturgy, poetry and journalism. The ideas of national freedom, social equality, enlightenment and humanism are leading in his work. The theme of women occupies a special place in Jabbarli's literary activity. He presents women not only within the family, but also as active participants in the development of society.

Jafar Jabbarli's female images are of great importance in Azerbaijani literature as an artistic expression of the idea of women's freedom. Through his heroes, the role of women in society was re-evaluated, ideals such as literacy, enlightenment, freedom and equality were brought to the fore. The images of Sevil and Almaz are not only artistic images, but also symbols of the historical development of Azerbaijani women.

The purpose of writing the article is to analyze Jafar Jabbarli's female images from an artistic-aesthetic, psychological and social perspective, and to determine their significance in Azerbaijani literature.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks are defined:

✓ To study the state of the women's issue in the socio-political conditions of the period in which Jabbarli lived;

✓ To analyze the principles of creating female images in the writer's dramatic works;

✓ To reveal the artistic expression of women's freedom and enlightenment ideas in the works of "Sevil" and "Almaz";

✓ To determine the socio-psychological functions of female images in other works;

✓ To evaluate the symbolic role of Jabbarli's women in the history of the development of Azerbaijani women, etc.

During the research, literary-historical, comparative analysis, textual studies and systematic approach methods were used.

Keywords: Jafar Jabbarli, women's freedom, women's rights, abolition of illiteracy, women's involvement in education, enlightenment, freedom, equality, etc.

The image of women has been one of the important and leading themes in the history of Azerbaijani literature. Although women's images have been presented from various angles in the work of poets and writers for centuries, they have mainly been limited to the family-domestic framework. Since the beginning of the 20th century, the issue of women has come to the center of attention in socio-political and cultural life, and the idea of women's freedom has become one of the main themes of national literature. Jafar Jabbarli took one of the most important steps in this direction.

Jafar Jabbarli is not only one of the founders of Azerbaijani dramaturgy, but also a carrier of the ideas of national renaissance. His female images are not only artistic in nature, but also play the role of the embodiment of ideas such as enlightenment, social awakening, and national freedom. In his works such as "Sevil", "Almaz", "Od Gelini", the fate of female heroes is taken together with the development of society, and their changes are identified with the progress of the people. (1, p.27)

The study of Jabbarli's female images is also relevant for the modern era. Because these images are not only an artistic reflection of a historical stage, but also an ideological factor influencing the formation of the socio-public position of modern women.

The object of the study is the images of women in Jafar Jabbarli's dramaturgical heritage, and the subject

is the artistic characteristics of the images, the social and ideological burden they carry in the work.

First, let's look at Jafar Jabbarli's creativity and the socio-political context of the period. What was Jafar Jabbarli's role in the development of Azerbaijani dramaturgy?

Jafar Jabbarli (1899–1934) is one of the brightest representatives of national dramaturgy in Azerbaijani literature. His works were the heralds of national awakening, the ideas of freedom and progress. Jabbarli brought to literature the enlightenment of the people, the equal place of women in society, and the struggle for national freedom.

He created a new stage in the national theater by synthesizing the traditions of classical Eastern literature with Western dramaturgy. In Jabbarli's dramaturgy, conflicts are not only of an individual-domestic nature, but are also presented as an artistic reflection of social and national issues. (2, p.39)

At the beginning of the 20th century, the situation of women in Azerbaijan was difficult. Early marriage, polygamy, and illiteracy were widespread. Women lived in a state of isolation from public life and without rights. The enlightenment movement that began in the last century brought the issue of women's liberation to the agenda at the beginning of the 20th century. The idea of women's liberation was reflected in the works of intellectuals such as Hasan bey Zardabi, Mirza Fatali Akhundzade, and Uzeyir Hajibeyli.

Jafar Jabbarli continued this tradition, developed it further, and presented women as active social forces in society.

As we look at the characteristic features of Jafar Jabbarli's female characters, we see that these characters undergo an evolutionary process within a certain period of time and were able to join the struggle for their rights.

One of the main tasks facing Azerbaijani literature at the beginning of the 20th century was to educate the people and raise the issue of women's liberation. Jafar Jabbarli is one of the writers who took the most brilliant and courageous steps in this field. Her play "Sevil" (1928) is considered the pinnacle of the theme of women in Azerbaijani dramaturgy, especially the idea of women's freedom. This work, due to its artistic and social content, was a turning point in our national literature and artistically confirmed the new social status of women.

The theme of the play "Sevil" is the Azerbaijani woman's liberation from the clutches of old traditions and entering a new, free and enlightened life. The work focuses on the fate of women against the background of social changes in society.

The main character of the work, Sevil, is initially a woman without rights and occupying an unworthy position within the family. She is oppressed by her husband Balash, lives in an illiterate and socially closed environment. However, over time, Sevil changes – she accepts the challenges of society, discovers her inner strength and becomes a fighting, free woman. This line of development reveals the main theme of the play – the transition of a woman from lawlessness to freedom. (3, p.92)

In addition to family-domestic relations, socio-political events also play a major role in the development of the theme in the work. Jabbarli shows that the fate of a woman is not limited only to the family, her freedom is closely connected with the progress of the entire nation.

The main idea of the drama "Sevil" is to defend women's freedom, enlightenment and equal participation in public life. The ideological burden of the work is manifested in several important moments:

- ✓ Women's freedom and progress – Jabbarli presents women's freedom as a necessary condition for the progress of the nation. The development of Sevil is shown as a symbol of the progress of all Azerbaijani women.

- ✓ The clash of old and new life – The image of Balash represents old age, backwardness, discrimination against women. Sevil is the embodiment of innovation, progress and the idea of modernity. This conflict forms the ideological basis of the work.

- ✓ The role of enlightenment and literacy – The enlightenment of women is particularly emphasized in the work. Jabbarli shows that literacy and social consciousness are the main factors that save women from slavery.

- ✓ The scene of throwing off the veil – this event, which is the culmination of the work, is not just a household detail, but also has a symbolic meaning. Here, the woman's escape from slavery and the step

taken by society towards progress are expressed. (4, p.75)

This play reflects not only the fate of a woman, but also symbolizes the path of freedom and renewal of an entire people. Jabbarli artistically revives the historical development path of Azerbaijani women through the image of Sevil. The idea of the work is relevant not only for its time, but also for today.

Jafar Jabbarli's play "Sevil" is one of the strongest expressions of the idea of women's liberation in Azerbaijani literature. The theme of the work - the development of women from lawlessness to freedom - has become one of the most important problems of national literature. The idea of the work is connected with the enlightenment of women, the affirmation of their equal position in public life.

The image of Sevil is not only a fictional heroine, but also a symbol of Azerbaijani women, an artistic expression of the path to freedom and progress. Therefore, "Sevil" can be assessed not only as a dramatic work, but also as a socio-political manifesto.

Let us pay attention to the writer's next work "Almaz", which deals with the issue of the role and rights of women in society. The play "Almaz", written by the writer in 1931, is one of the important works reflecting the formation of Azerbaijani women in the new social environment with the ideas of enlightenment. In this play, women are presented not only within the family, but also as educators, intellectuals and public figures.

The theme of the play "Almaz" is the struggle against ignorance and superstition in the Azerbaijani rural environment, the active position of women in the new social conditions, and their educational activities. The main character of the play, Almaz, focuses on the role of literacy, science, and education in society through the image of the teacher Almaz.

The events take place in the village, and an environment dominated by old customs, superstitions, and ignorance is depicted here. Almaz brings a new breath to this environment. As a teacher, she tries to spread educational work in the village, educate women and children, and free the rural population from ignorance. Thus, the theme of the play is related to both the mission of women's education and the struggle for the renewal of society.

The main idea of the play "Almaz" is that the progress of society is connected with education, women's education, and their active participation in public life. Jabbarli shows that:

- ✓ Education is the main path to progress – through the image of Almaz, the author emphasizes that literacy and education play a decisive role in the development of society.

- ✓ The place of women in public life – In the work, women are presented not as passive beings, but as active intellectuals and public figures. Teacher Almaz fights against ignorance in the village and influences the formation of the future generation.

- ✓ The struggle between the old and the new – The idea of the work is also based on the confrontation between ignorance and enlightenment, backwardness and

progress. Almaz represents innovation, science and enlightenment, and her opponents represent backwardness and superstition. (5, p.113)

The image of Almaz is a new face of a woman in national dramaturgy - she is not only a woman in the family, but also an educator of future generations, a guide to the path of progress.

Jafar Jabbarli's play "Almaz" reflects a new stage of the image of a woman in Azerbaijani dramaturgy. The theme of the work - the activity of a woman in a rural environment as an educator and intellectual - artistically expresses the increase in the role of a woman in public life. The idea of the work is related to enlightenment, literacy and women's freedom.

The image of Almaz is presented as a symbol of a modern Azerbaijani woman, a symbol of progress. From this point of view, "Almaz" is not only a drama, but also an artistic manifesto of a woman's new position in society.

There is no work by Jafar Jabbarli that does not contain a female image. "The Bride of Fire" (1922) - The image of Shavkat is the embodiment of love, selflessness and loyalty. "Aydın" (1919) – female images are presented as carriers of innovative, progressive ideas. "In 1905" (1921) – female heroes are depicted together with the people in the struggle for national liberation.

In these works, women are not depicted as passive beings, but sometimes as forces that change the course of events.

As for the artistic and aesthetic merits of Jafar Jabbarli's female images, it can be said that the main feature of these women is their internal change and psychological development. Sevil's development from ignorance to enlightenment, Almaz's fighting and strong-willed character are developed with psychological depth.

Jabbarli's women are both connected to national roots and carriers of universal humanist ideas. Their struggle for freedom and equality has a universal character.

The above-mentioned images of Sevil and Almaz are not only artistic images, but also ideological symbols. They embody the historical development path of Azerbaijani women, their transition from illiteracy to enlightenment, from slavery to freedom. (6, p.47)

In conclusion, we can say that Jafar Jabbarli's female images are the strongest exponents of the idea of women's freedom in Azerbaijani literature. His heroes are the bearers of the ideas of enlightenment, progress, and equality. Jabbarli's female images opened a new stage in national dramaturgy and had a great impact on the rise of the social status of Azerbaijani women.

The images of "Sevil" and "Almaz" have become artistic symbols of women's freedom in national literature. These images are still relevant today and are valuable in terms of illuminating the path of development of modern Azerbaijani women.

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